

Original Article

Efforts Made by School Teachers to Inculcate Environmental Values among Students: A Study

Dr. Nanaware Kiran Vishnu

Associate Professor, Department of Education, Abhinav Education Society's, College of Education, S. No. 13, Katraj – Dehu Road Bypass, Ambegaon Bk., Pune. (MS), INDIA

Abstract

"The Earth will not continue to offer its harvest, except with faithful stewardship!" As said by John Paul II, we the human beings should respect the Environment and Save Earth today for tomorrow. In this connection the role of Education and teachers is very important. Teachers are the agents of Social, cultural and Environmental change. They give shapes to our children, inculcate the ideal values among them to be a responsible citizen and the leaders of tomorrow. The objective of this research is, to study the efforts and initiatives taken by the school teachers to inculcate the Environment, values, awareness, roles, responsibilities and the duties to protect, conserve and respect our nature. Researcher has studied that, how the school teachers are trying to inculcate the environmental values among students, through the teaching – learning, organizing, and conducting various co & Extra – curricular activities related to protect, conserve and preserve our environment. Researcher has used Survey method of Research with Single group design. He has used purposive sampling method for this study. For data collection he used questionnaire and the Mean, Mode, median and Percentage as statistical tools for data analysis. The findings and conclusion of this study are mentioned at the end of this Research paper and its showing the positive initiatives and efforts are taken by the Teachers as responsible agents of Nature.

Keywords: Efforts, Inculcation, Environmental Values, School Teachers, Students.

Address for correspondence: Dr. Nanaware Kiran Vishnu, Associate Professor, Department of Education, Abhinav Education Society's, College of Education, S. No. 13, Katraj – Dehu Road Bypass, Ambegaon Bk., Pune. (MS), INDIA

Email: kvnabhinavbedcollege@gmail.com

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INTRODUCTION:

"The nation that destroy its soil, destroy itself. Forests are the lungs of our land purifying the air and giving fresh strength to our people."

– **Franklin D Roosevelt.**

This thought makes us aware about our roles and responsibilities regarding the protection and conservation of the environment. The dreams, visions, targets and aims of any nation are naturally reflect in its Educational Curriculum. The future of a nation is shaped by its education system. So, the Educational Institutes are the hubs to achieve the dreams and visions of nation and it can be achieved through the effective implementation of the Curriculums.

Need and Importance of development Environmental Values among the Students:

Environmental education is important because it helps students develop a sense of responsibility towards the environment and the skills

needed to live sustainably. The environmental education can develop the values, skills, attitude and life skills among the students through the conducting various Co and Extra- curricular and environment protection related activities as below :

- **Environmental awareness:** Students learn and aware about the issues generated like global warming, draughts, floods, heavy rainfalls, its causes, precautions and measures to reduce it, how to reduce waste, conserve energy, and preserve natural resources. Such kind of topics are included in the syllabus and also conduct the Hands-on activities to aware the students.
- **Critical thinking:** Teachers can develop the life skills among the Students. They can develop the ability to analyze and solve environmental problems. E.g.: Debate competition, elocution competitions, Essay writing Competitions, Quiz competition..etc.

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- **Respect for nature:** Teacher can develop the attitude, values among the Students. Also they can learn about the interdependence of living things and how to protect them. E.g. : Environment , Geography Day celebration, Tree /Sapling Plantation, formation of clubs to protect environment, animals, Water Resources..etc.
- **Academic skills:** Teachers can develop skills like decision-making, thought provoking, analytical thinking, and synthesizing information.
- **Social skills:** Teachers can conduct the activities like co-operative learning, Team spirit, co-ordination, collaborate and work with each other in a team. Eg.: Social Service Camps, Natural Disaster Rescue Teams, Environment Clubs...etc.

Role of Schools and Educational Institutes:

Our schools and Educational Institutes are the laboratories to give shape and foster the values among tomorrows Citizens. By nurturing environmental values and awareness in schools, we not only equip future generations with the knowledge and skills to protect our planet but also cultivate a mind-sets of responsibility and respect towards nature, that can extend beyond the classroom into their everyday lives. Creating a school culture that values sustainability is crucial. This can involve initiatives like reducing waste, conserving energy, and promoting eco-friendly practices. Engaging students in green initiatives such as setting up composting systems, organizing tree planting events, or participating in community clean-ups empowers them to take positive action. Nurturing environmental responsibilities involves inculcating a deep sense of responsibility and care for the environment in individuals and communities.

This can be achieved through education, awareness, and practical initiatives. In schools, fostering environmental stewardship starts with integrating sustainability into the curriculum. Students can learn about the inter and intra connectivity of ecosystems, the impact of human activities on the environment, biodiversity and the importance of conservation. Hands-on activities such as gardening, creation of environment protection clubs, 3R' and recycling programs, and nature walks, co & extra-curricular activities, projects, can deepen their understanding and appreciation of nature.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To Design the test to check the efforts made by School Teacher for inculcation of Environmental Values.
2. To conduct the test on School Teachers to check the efforts made by them for inculcation of Environmental Values among the Students.
3. To collect, analyse, interpret the data with its findings and conclusions about the efforts made by School teachers to inculcate Environmental Values among the Students.

DEFINITIONS: (Conceptual & Operational)

Efforts (Conceptual Definition):

Physical or mental activity needed to achieve something, or an attempt to do something.

- Cambridge / Oxford Dictionary.

(Operational Definition)

The use of different Teaching – learning methods, strategies, techniques, plans, projects , activities by School teachers to inculcate, develop, promote values related to sustainable development , Environment Protection, conservation, preservation among the school students are considered as efforts.

School Teacher: (Dictionary Meaning)

A person whose, job is to teach, especially in a Primary or Secondary level school.

(Operational Definition)

A person who, teaches school students from 1st standard to 12th standard.

Inculcation: (Definition)

Inculcation refers to the act of teaching or instilling something, such as values, habits, or knowledge, through persistent and repetitive instruction. It is often associated with the goal of firmly embedding these ideas or principles in someone's mind.

Dictionary Meaning:

Merriam-Webster: *The act of teaching and impressing something upon the mind by frequent repetition or admonition.*

- **Oxford English Dictionary:** *The process of instilling ideas, attitudes, or habits through persistent instruction.*

Environmental Values: (Definition)

Environmental values refer to the principles and standards that guide behaviours and decisions to preserve and protect the natural world, advocating for sustainability, conservation, and stewardship.

These values often emphasize the importance of balancing ecological health, economic growth, and social well-being for current and future generations. Understanding and embracing environmental values can lead to positive actions such as reducing waste, conserving water, and promoting renewable energy.

- Oxford /Cambridge Dictionary.

School Student: (Conceptual Definition)

School students in India are children who are enrolled in a school and are in the process of learning. The Indian Constitution guarantees free and compulsory education for children between the ages of 6 and 14.

Students (Operational Definition) :

The students, who are getting education from 1st Standard to till the 12th Standard.

A Study : (Conceptual Definition)

The term "study" functions both as a noun and a verb, encompassing various meanings related to learning, examination, and research or a complete investigation and analysis of a subject, phenomenon, etc.

- Britannica Dictionary

Assumptions:

1. The curriculum of School Education reflects the values of Environment Protection, conservation and Sustainable Development.
2. The content included in Textbooks and all the Co and Extra-Curricular Activities organized and conducted on school level, some activities are related to promote Environmental Values.
3. The Teachers are trying their best to conduct various Activities related to develop Environmental Values among the school students.
4. The thoughts, behavior, sharing views, attitude of Teachers is the real reflection on students.

HYPOTHESIS:

- i) **Research Hypothesis:** There are various efforts made by school teachers to inculcate the Environmental Values among the Students
- ii) **Null Hypothesis:** There are no more efforts made by the School teachers to inculcate the values among the Students.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

The present study was conducted on the School Teachers, those are teaching in any curriculum pattern and the both levels of Curriculum i.e. Primary and Secondary schools of Haveli Tehsil of Pune District. The result of the study will be applicable to all Teachers.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:

1. The Psychological aspects like attention, motivation, interest are beyond the control of Researcher.
2. The effect in achievement due to personal guidance and coaching will not be considered.
3. The difference between the efforts taken by teachers may differ the achievement.
4. The conclusion of the study will depend upon the analysis of the responses given by respondents.

DELIMITATIONS:

- 1.) This study is conducted only in Haveli, Bhore and Mulashi Tahasil of Pune District.
- 2.) The present study results are applicable to the 65 (Sixty -Four) Teacher of various schools of 04 (Four)

Procedure of Research:

- **Data Analysis:** The data analyzed by researcher as follows and presented in Table. :

Haveli, Bhore, Maval and Mulashi Tahasil of Pune District.

3.) The present study is related to checking the efforts of 80 Teachers made for the inculcation of Environmental Values among the School Students.

RESEARCH METHOD OF THE STUDY:

For this Present study Researcher has used Survey Research Method.

RESEARCH DESIGN:

Single Group Design – Pre –test has used.

Population and Sampling:

Purposive sampling method was adopted for the present study.

Population:

All the Teachers teaching in different schools and different Curriculum Pattern adopted by respective schools in the Haveli, Bhore and Mulshi, Maval Tahasil, Dist. Pune, Maharashtra is the population for the present study.

Sample:

65 Teachers from 04 (Four) Tehsils of Pune District i.e.Haveli, Bhore , Maval and Mulashi were selected as a sample by using purposive sampling method-(Non-probability sampling method) was used.

Tools for Data Collection:

A questionnaire is developed by Researcher to study the efforts made by school teacher to inculcate Environmental values among the School Students. It has contains 30 questions to check the initiatives made for the effective implementation of Teaching – learning process, conduction of activities related to Environment Protection, conservation and preservation in school. Also, the questionnaire checks the activities like: organization of various campaigns, clubs and awareness sessions conducted by teachers for the welfare of environment and sustainable development, roles responsibilities and attitude of school Teachers.

Statistical Tools:

Researcher has made use of Mean, Mode, Median and Percentage from descriptive statistical tools.

Table No. 01: Statistical analysis of Collected Data regarding the efforts made by teachers to inculcate Environmental Values among Students.

S. No.	Statistical Techniques	Score out of 30				
		Average	Score Range (Min-Max)	Median	Mode	Percentage (21 – 30)
1.						
2.		25	14 - 30	25	25	89.23%

DATA INTERPRETATION:

The above table shows the details of the statistical analysis of the scores received from the Test, conducted by Researcher. This test having 30 Marks, out of 30 Marks Maximum Marks achieved by Student is 30 and Minimum Marks are 14. The Average of the Scores achieved by 65 Students is 25 and the Mean of this test is 25 also. The 58 Teachers out of 65 achieved the score in the above test in between 21 to 30 Marks out of 30.

CONCLUSION:

The efforts made by the School Teachers to inculcate the Environmental values among the school students of Primary and on the Secondary level in different Medium schools having different Patterns of Curriculums from Pune District , especially Four (04) Tehsils i.e. Haveli, Bhore, Mulashi & Maval. On the basis of above table the Median / Average of the Scores of Teachers, Researcher.

Table No. 02

Obtained Scores by Teachers and No. of Teachers in the Test conducted to study the efforts made by teachers to inculcate Environmental Values among Students.

S. No.	No. of Teachers	Marks obtained by Teachers out of 30
1	1	14
2	2	18
3	4	20
4	3	21
5	7	22
6	5	23
7	3	24
8	12	25
9	10	26
10	9	27
11	3	28
12	4	29
13	1	30

Graph No. 01: Obtained Scores by Teachers and No. of Teachers in the Test conducted to study the efforts made by teachers to inculcate Environmental Values among Students.

Obtained Scores by Teachers and No. of Teachers in the Test conducted to study the efforts made by teachers to inculcate Environmental Values among Students.

As per, the above graph, it is showing that the Score of Test out of the 30 Marks. The 65 school teachers had solved this Test. According to the values are showing in the Graph Minimum 14 Marks are

achieved by One teacher and Maximum score achieved 30 out of 30 Marks are 01 Teacher, so the range of Marks achieved in this Test is 14 – 30.

On the basis of above graph, The Scores is of test achieved by 65 Teachers classified in 13 values, and its Mean score of is the 25.

Conclusion:

On the basis of above data analysis and its interpretation researcher is reach to this conclusion , that the out of the 65 Teachers from four different Tehsils of Pune district 28 were performed in

Excellent grade, 30 teachers performed in Good Grade, 06 teachers were performed in satisfactory grade and only one in the grade of Average. Also no one teachers is performed in poor grade.

So, the conclusion is that the out of 65 teachers 58 (89.07%) are taking rigorous efforts to promote and inculcate the Environmental values among the school students.

Table No. 03:

The classification of the teachers achievements in test scores based on grades.

Gradation: Researcher has classified the Scores achieved by Teacher in the Test out of 30 Marks as below:

S. No.	Class Intervals	No. of School Teachers	Percentage (/ 65 * 100)	Grade
	0 to 10	00	0.00%	Poor
	11 to 15	01	1.53%	Average
	16 to 20	06	9.23%	Satisfactory
	21 to 25	30	46.15%	Good
	26 to 30	28	43.07%	Excellent
	Total No. of Respondents	65	100.00%	

Table No. 02: The Grades on the basis of Teachers achievements in the Test Scores.

Data Interpretation:

The values shown in the table are on the basis of Graph)

1. Not a single Teacher is performed under the Poor grade.
2. only **01 (1.53%)** Teacher was shown Average performance.
3. **06 (9.23%)** Teachers were performed under Satisfactory Grade.
4. **30 (46.15%)** Teachers were performed under the Goodgrade, and
5. **28 (43.07%)** Teachers were performed score under the grade of Excellent.

CONCLUSION :

As per the above data interpretation and on the basis of Table properties with the help of Graphical presentation , the efforts made by the Shool teachers are really appreciable.

FINDINGS :

- The school teachers are taking rigourous initiatives and efforts to inculcate the environmental values among the students.

- For effective implementation and inculcation of Environmental Values among the students teachers are following the idalogies and eco – frinedly behavioural patterns, attitudes , ettiquests, protocols not only in school premises or infront of students but also in their personal and daily life.
- On the basis of reveieved responses, reserchers concludes that, school teachers are taking efforts to inculcate the environmental values among the students, while teaching –learning , conducting Co - curricular & Extra - curricular activities, various campagins, drives to save , protect, preserve and conserve the Environmental resources Principles.

SUGGESTIONS:

1. The Curricular framing agencies should include more and more project based, Hands-on activities related to develop Environment awareness, values, skills, attitude among the students.
2. The Schools and Educational Institutes have need to organize and promote to Heads and theirs teachers to effective organization and conduction

of all the activities related to Environment awareness, preservation, protection, conservation and for the Sustainable Development of nature/earth.

- Teachers have to develop the students insights, attitudes, skills, knowledge, in kindness of Environment protection. Also, co -relate all subject contents while teaching -learning process and conducting various co & Extra - curricular activities to develop students personalities as an agents of nature lover or saver.

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